

PRIME CORDIAL GRAPHS**M. Bhuvaneshwari*, Selvam Avadayappan** & S. Gowsalya*****Research Department of Mathematics, Virudhunagar Hindu Nadars' Senthikumara Nadar College,
Virudhunagar, Tamilnadu**Cite This Article:** M. Bhuvaneshwari, Selvam Avadayappan & S. Gowsalya, "Prime Cordial Graphs", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Special Issue, February, Page Number 54-61, 2017.**Abstract:**

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. A prime cordial labeling of G with vertex set V is a bijection f from V to $\{1, 2, \dots, |V|\}$ such that if each edge uv is assigned the label 1 when $\gcd(f(u), f(v)) = 1$ and 0 otherwise, then the difference between the number of edges labeled with 1 and the number of edges labeled with 0 is at most 1. A graph which admits prime cordial labeling is called a prime cordial graph. In this paper, we prove that some corona graphs are prime cordial.

Key Words : Labeling, Cordial Labeling & Prime Cordial Labeling

1. Introduction:

The graphs considered in this paper are finite, simple, undirected and connected. For the notations and terminology, we refer [3]. Let C_n and P_n denote the cycle and path on n vertices respectively. Let $K_{1,n}$ and $B_{n,n}$ denote the star and bistar on n vertices respectively. The corona $G_1 \circ G_2$ of two graphs G_1 and G_2 is the graph G obtained by taking one copy of G_1 which has p_1 vertices and p_1 copies of G_2 and then joining the i^{th} vertex of G_1 to every vertex in the i^{th} copy of G_2 . For example, the graph $C_6 \circ K_2$ is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

An edge $uv \in E(G)$ is subdivided if the edge uv is deleted and a new vertex x (called a subdivision vertex) is added together with the new edges ux and vx . A *subdivision graph* $S(G)$ of a graph G is obtained from G by subdividing all edges of G exactly once. For example, the subdivision graph $S(K_{1,6})$ is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

In 1960's Rosa [7] introduced the concept of graph labeling. A *graph labeling* is an assignment of numbers to the vertices or edges or both satisfying some constraints. A *vertex labeling* of a graph G is an assignment f of labels to the vertices of G that induces for each edge uv a label depending on the vertex label $f(u)$ and $f(v)$. The two best known labelings are graceful labeling and harmonious labeling [5]. Cordial labeling is a variation of both graceful and harmonious labelings [4]. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. A mapping $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is called *binary vertex labeling* of G and $f(v)$ is called the *label* of the vertex v of G under f . For an edge $e = uv$, the *induced edge labeling* $f^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is given by $f^*(e) = |f(u) - f(v)|$. Let $v_f(0)$ and $v_f(1)$ be the number of vertices of G having labels 0 and 1 respectively under f and let $e_f(0)$ and $e_f(1)$ be the number of edges of G having labels 0 and 1 respectively under f^* . The concept of cordial labeling was introduced by Cahit [4]. A binary vertex labeling of a graph G is called a *cordial labeling* if $|v_f(0) - v_f(1)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(0) - e_f(1)| \leq 1$. A graph G is *cordial* if it admits cordial labeling. The concept of prime cordial labeling was introduced by Sundaram, Ponraj, and Somasundaram [8].

A *prime cordial labeling* of a graph G with vertex set V is a bijection f from V to $\{1,2,\dots,|V|\}$ such that if each edge uv is assigned the label 1 when $\gcd(f(u), f(v)) = 1$ and 0 otherwise, then the number of edges labeled with 1 and the number of edges labeled with 0 differ by at most 1. A graph which admits prime cordial labeling is called a *prime cordial graph*. Many results on prime cordial labelings have been established in [1, 2, 6, 9, 10]. For example, a prime cordial labeling of a graph is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

In this paper, we prove that the corona graphs $P_n \circ K_1$, $C_n \circ K_1$, $K_{1,n} \circ K_1$, $S(K_{1,n}) \circ K_1$, $B_{n,n} \circ K_1$ and some other graphs admit prime cordial labeling.

2. Main Results:

Theorem 2.1: *The graph $P_n \circ K_1$ is prime cordial.*

Proof: Let $V(P_n \circ K_1) = \{u_i, v_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the vertex set and Let $E(P_n \circ K_1) = \{u_i v_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1} ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1\}$ be the edge set of $P_n \circ K_1$.

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1,2,\dots,2n\}$ by $f(u_i) = 2i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$ and $f(v_i) = 2i-1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Then the induced edge labelings are $f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1$ and $f^*(u_i v_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Thus, $e_f(0) = n-1$, $e_f(1) = n$.

It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph $P_n \circ K_1$ is prime cordial. The case when $n = 7$ is illustrated in Figure 4.

A Prime Cordial Labeling of $P_7 \circ K_1$

Figure 4

Theorem 2.2: *The graph $C_n \circ K_1$ admits prime cordial labeling.*

Proof: Let $V(C_n \circ K_1) = \{u_i, v_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(C_n \circ K_1) = \{u_n u_1, u_i v_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1} ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1\}$ be the edge set of $C_n \circ K_1$.

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1,2,\dots,2n\}$ by $f(u_i) = 2i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$ and $f(v_i) = 2i-1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Then the induced edge labelings are $f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1$, $f^*(u_n u_1) = 0$ and $f^*(u_i v_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Thus, $e_f(0) = e_f(1) = n$.

It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph $C_n \circ K_1$ is prime cordial. The case when $n = 6$ is illustrated in Figure 5.

A Prime Cordial Labeling of $C_6 \circ K_1$

Figure 5

Theorem 2.3: The graph $K_{1,n} \circ K_1$ is prime cordial.

Proof: Let $V(K_{1,n} \circ K_1) = \{v, w, u_i, v_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(K_{1,n} \circ K_1) = \{vv_i, v_iu_i, vw ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the edge set of $K_{1,n} \circ K_1$.

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 2n+2\}$ by $f(v) = 2, f(w) = 1, f(u_i) = 2i + 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$ and $f(v_i) = 2i + 2 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Then the induced edge labelings are $f^*(vv_i) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f^*(v_iu_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$ and $f^*(vw) = 1$.

Thus, $e_f(0) = n, e_f(1) = n+1$.

It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph $K_{1,n} \circ K_1$ is prime cordial.

The case when $n = 6$ is illustrated in Figure 6.

A Prime Cordial Labeling of $K_{1,6} \circ K_1$

Figure 6

Theorem 2.4: The graph $S(K_{1,n}) \circ K_1$ is prime cordial.

Proof: Let $V(S(K_{1,n}) \circ K_1) = \{v, w, u_i, v_i, x_i, y_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(S(K_{1,n}) \circ K_1) = \{vv_i, v_iu_i, vw, v_ix_i, u_iy_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the edge set of $S(K_{1,n}) \circ K_1$.

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 4n+2\}$ by $f(v) = 2, f(w) = 1, f(u_i) = 4i + 2 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f(v_i) = 4i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f(x_i) = 4i - 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$ and $f(y_i) = 4i + 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Then the induced edge labelings are

$$f^*(vw) = 1$$

$$f^*(vv_i) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f^*(v_iu_i) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f^*(v_ix_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f^*(u_iy_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n.$$

Thus, $e_f(0) = 2n$, $e_f(1) = 2n+1$. It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph $S(K_{1,n}) \circ K_1$ is prime cordial. For example, a prime cordial labeling of $S(K_{1,6}) \circ K_1$ is shown in Figure 7.

A Prime Cordial Labeling of $S(K_{1,6}) \circ K_1$

Figure 7

Theorem 2.5: The graph $B_{n,n} \circ K_1$ is prime cordial.

Proof: Let $V(B_{n,n} \circ K_1) = \{u, v, u_i, v_i, x, y ; 1, \leq i, \leq 2n\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(B_{n,n} \circ K_1) = \{ux, vy, uu_{2i-1}, u_{2i-1}u_{2i}, vv_{2i-1}, v_{2i-1}v_{2i}, uv ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the edge set of $B_{n,n} \circ K_1$.

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 4n+4\}$ by $f(x) = 3, f(y) = 2, f(u) = 1, f(v) = 4,$

$$f(u_{2i-1}) = 4i + 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f(u_{2i}) = 4i + 3 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f(v_{2i-1}) = 4i + 2 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n \text{ and } f(v_{2i}) = 4i + 4 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n.$$

Then the induced edge labelings are

$$f^*(ux) = 1, f^*(uv) = 1, f^*(vy) = 0, f^*(uu_{2i-1}) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f^*(u_{2i-1}u_{2i}) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f^*(vv_{2i-1}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n \text{ and } f^*(v_{2i-1}v_{2i}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n.$$

Thus, $e_f(0) = 2n+1, e_f(1) = 2n+2$.

It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph $B_{n,n} \circ K_1$ is prime cordial. For example, a prime cordial labeling of $B_{4,4} \circ K_1$ is shown in Figure 8.

A Prime Cordial Labeling of $B_{4,4} \circ K_1$

Figure 8

Let G be any graph. Then $G * K_{1,n}$ is the graph obtained by identifying a vertex of G with central vertex of $K_{1,n}$. For example, the graph $C_5 * K_{1,7}$ is shown in Figure 9.

The graph $C_5 * K_{1,7}$

Figure 9

Theorem 2.6: The graph $C_n * K_{1,n+m}$ is prime cordial.

Proof Let $V(C_n * K_{1,n+m}) = \{u_i, v_i, v_j ; 1, \leq i, \leq n ; n+1, \leq j, \leq n+m\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(C_n * K_{1,n+m}) = \{u_i u_{i+1}, u_i v_i, u_i v_j ; 1, \leq i \leq n, ; n+1, \leq j, \leq n+m\}$ be the edge set of $C_n * K_{1,n+m}$.

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 3n\}$ by $f(u_i) = 2i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$
 $f(v_i) = 2i - 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$ and $f(v_j) = n + j ; n + 1, \leq j, \leq n + m$.

Then the induced edge labelings are $f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n - 1, f^*(u_n u_1) = 0$

$f^*(u_i v_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f^*(u_i v_{n+2i}) = 0 ; n + 1, \leq j, \leq n + m$ and $f^*(u_i v_{n+2i-1}) = 1 ; n + 1, \leq j, \leq n + m$.

We note that $e_f(0) = e_f(1) = n + 2$ if $m \equiv 0(mod 2)$

$e_f(1) = n + 3, e_f(0) = n + 2$ if $m \equiv 1(mod 2)$

It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph $C_n * K_{1,n+m}$ is prime cordial. The cases when $m = 3$ and $m = 4$ are illustrated in Figure 10 and 11 respectively

A Prime Cordial Labeling of $C_4 * K_{1,4+3}$

Figure 10

A Prime Cordial Labeling of $C_4 * K_{1,4+4}$

Figure 11

Let J_n denote the graph with vertex set $V(J_n) = \{v, w, v_i, u_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ and the edge set $E(J_n) = \{u_n u_1, v_n v_1, vw, vu_i, u_i v_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1} ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1\}$. For example, the graph J_5 is shown in Figure 12.

The graph J_5

Figure 12

Theorem 2.7: *The graph J_n is prime cordial.*

Proof: Let $V(J_n) = \{v, w, v_i, u_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(J_n) = \{u_n u_1, v_n v_1, vw, vu_i, u_i v_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1} ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1\}$ be the edge set of J_n .

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 2n+2\}$ by $f(v) = 2, f(w) = 3, f(v_i) = 1, f(u_i) = 2i+2 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$ and $f(v_i) = 2i+1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Then the induced edge labelings are $f^*(vw) = 1,$

$$f^*(vu_i) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1; f^*(u_n u_1) = 0$$

$$f^*(u_i v_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$$

$$f^*(v_i v_{i+1}) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1; \text{ and } f^*(v_n v_1) = 1.$$

Thus, $e_f(0) = 2n, e_f(1) = 2n+1.$

It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph J_n is prime cordial. For example, a prime cordial labeling of J_5 is shown in Figure 13.

A Prime Cordial Labeling of J_5

Figure 13

Let $V(J_n^2) = \{v, w, u_i, v_i, x_i, y_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(J_n^2) = \{u_n u_1, v_n v_1, x_n x_1, y_n y_1, vw, vu_i, u_i v_i, x_i y_i, u_i x_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1}, x_i x_{i+1}, y_i y_{i+1} ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1\}$ be the edge set of J_n^2 . For example, the graph J_5^2 is shown in Figure 14.

The graph J_n^2
Figure 14

Theorem 2.8: The graph J_n^2 is prime cordial.

Proof: Let $V(J_n^2) = \{v, w, u_i, v_i, x_i, y_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\}$ be the vertex set and let $E(J_n^2) = \{u_n u_1, v_n v_1, x_n x_1, y_n y_1, vw, vu_i, u_i v_i, x_i y_i, u_i x_i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n\} \cup \{u_i u_{i+1}, v_i v_{i+1}, x_i x_{i+1}, y_i y_{i+1} ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1\}$ be the edge set of J_n^2 .

Define $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, 4n+2\}$ by $f(v) = 2, f(w) = 3, f(v_i) = 1, f(u_i) = 2i+2 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$
 $f(v_i) = 2i+1 ; 2, \leq i, \leq n$
 $f(x_i) = 2n+2+2i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$
 $f(u_i) = 2n+1+2i ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$.

Then the induced edge labeling are $f^*(vw) = 1, f^*(vu_i) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n ; f^*(u_n u_1) = 0$

$f^*(u_i v_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f^*(v_i v_{i+1}) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1 ; f^*(v_n v_1) = 1$

$f^*(x_i x_{i+1}) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1 ; f^*(x_n x_1) = 0$

$f^*(u_i x_i) = 0 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f^*(x_i y_i) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n$

$f^*(y_i y_{i+1}) = 1 ; 1, \leq i, \leq n-1$ and $f^*(y_n y_1) = 0$ if $\gcd(2n+3, 4n+1) > 1$
 $= 1$ otherwise.

if $f^*(y_n y_1) = 0$ then $e_f(0) = 4n+1, e_f(1) = 4n$

else $e_f(0) = 4n, e_f(1) = 4n+1$

It follows that f is a prime cordial labeling. Thus the graph J_n^2 is prime cordial. For example, a prime cordial labeling of J_5^2 is shown in Figure 15.

A Prime Cordial Labeling of J_5^2

(Figure 15)

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1. J. Baskar Babujee and L. Shobana, Prime Cordial Labeling, International Review of Pure and Applied Mathematics, 5(2) (2009), 277-282.
2. S. Babitha and J. Baskar Babujee, Prime Cordial Labeling and Duality, International Journal of Mathematical sciences, 7(1) (2013), 43-48.
3. R. Balakrishnan and K. Ranganathan, A Text Book of graph theory, Springer-verlag, New York, Inc., 1999.
4. I. Cahit, Cordial graphs: A weaker version of graceful and harmonious graphs, Ars Combinatoria, 23 (1987), 201-207.
5. J.A. Gallian, A Dynamic Survey of Graph Labeling, Electronic Journal of Combinatorics, 18 (2011), # DS6.
6. Haque, Kh.Md. Mominul, Xiaohui, Lin, Yuansheng, Yang, Pingzhong, Zhao, On the Prime cordial labeling of generalized Petersen graph, Utilitas Mathematica, 82 (2010), 71-79.
7. A.Rosa, On certain valuations of the vertices of a graph, Theory of Graphs Internet Symposium, Rome, July (1996) 349-355.
8. M. Sundaram, R. Ponraj and S. Somasundaram, Prime cordial labeling of graphs, Journal of the Indian Academy of Mathematics, 27(2) (2005), 373-390.
9. S. K. Vaidya, N.H. Shah, Some New Families of Prime Cordial Graphs, Journal of Mathematics Research, 3(4) (2011), November, 21-30.
10. S. K. Vaidya, P.L. Vihol, Prime cordial labeling for some cycle related graphs, International Journal of Open Problems in Computer Science and Mathematics, 3(5) (2010), December, 223-232.